

KEVLAR AND KEVLAR REINFORCED COMPOSITES MATERIALS AGING UNDER VARIOUS ENVIRONMENTS

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ABSTRACT

Kevlar 29 and Kevlar 49 fibers, Kevlar 49 composites and Kevlar strands were aging in various chemical or thermic environments. The results of this study show the good behaviour of Kevlar fiber and Kevlar resin materials in salt spray fog, sea water, solvents and grease. The Kevlar fiber moisture behaviour is good but the Kevlar composites moisture behaviour is moderate. Ultraviolet degradation of Kevlar can be extensive, and Kerosene degradation is important only for long time aging.

1 - INTRODUCTION

The more and more overworld use of Kevlar aramid fibers and Kevlar products brings up a usefull knowledge of those materials in many scientific departments. It seemed nevertheless that few studies had been realized according to Kevlar reinforced composites aging properties, except shorted tests (few hours of aging). It has appeared therefore interesting to study the long term behavior of Kevlar 49 and Kevlar 29 fibers, strands, and reinforced composites, under various chemical and thermal environments.

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2 - EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Materials

Different materials were used for this work :

- Kevlar 49 roving 4560 deniers
- Kevlar 29 roving 1500 deniers
- Kevlar 29 strands coming from Cordes Europe France Company (CEFOP 1, 1 TWA 3 ref.) these strands are braided with 8 Kevlar 29,1500 deniers rovings and are protected with a special polyurethane treatment.
- Kevlar 49/epoxy composites (R 79 resin)
- Kevlar 49/PSP composites (PSP 6022 resin)

Composites have been realized by filament winding around a flat mandrel (wet winding).

Exposure conditions (fig. 1)

Materials have been exposed to ultraviolet radiations in an Hanau type 150 Xenotest ; tests have been made following the NFT 51056 AFNOR standard test method during 500 h. Materials have been aged during 6 months in the JP1 Kerosene at 70°C.

Composites and fiber specimens have been also exposed to moisture (70°C 95% H₂O) during 5000 hours. Salt spray fog studies have been conducted in a special chamber during 5000 hours, following the AFNOR NFX 41002 Standard test Kevlar 29 roving and strands have been immersed in 4° sea water and in room temperature sea water (from TOULON).

Immersion test have been also undertaken with a solvent (benzene), a plasticiser (ethyl hexyl cebaçate), a grease (marine GAI grease), an hydraulic fluid (Pharinafic) which are used in marine applications. Immersion time was 1000 hours at room temperature.

Thermal shock resistance of impregnated Kevlar 49 roving (4560 den) has been studied as shown below :

Roving, strands and composites have been exposed to thermal cycles, (-40°C + 120°C) during 500 cycles. Each cycle exposure was 1 h 45 mn long, so 875 hours for the total test

Aging control tests

Roving and strands control tests were tensile strength measurement before and after aging. Tests were made with non-impregnated rovings and strands with special Instron pneumatic cord and yarn jaws (fig. 2). An interlaminar shear aging control test at 20°C and 120°C, and a flexure test (three point loading) were made for the composites.

Preliminary study

- Testing speed effect on the tensile strength

Tensile tests were made on Kevlar 49 rovings at the speed of 10 to 50 mm/mn. Results are shown below in table 1, and in Fig. 3.

TABLE 1
TESTING SPEED EFFECT

Tensile strength (Standard deviation) MPa

Gauge	Tensile speed	10	20	50
	mm gauge length mm/mn			
Non Impregnated Rovings	10	2110 (120)	2090 (120)	2030 (130)
	25	2080 (90)	2010 (120)	1970 (120)
	50	2030 (110)	2020 (120)	1950 (120)
	250	1670 (140)	1720 (160)	1720 (120)
Resin Impregnated rovings	250	3530 (140)	3550 (180)	3590 (160)

Testing speed incidence on the ultimate tensile strength of Kevlar rovings is quite small and there is a little decrease of properties (4%) with the little gauge lengths (up to 50 mm) when the testing speed increase.

BUNSELL and LAFFITTE work [2] shows that there is no testing speed influence from 0,1 to 500 mm/mn on Kevlar 29 single fiber.

- Tensile strength gauge length effect

We will call "gauge length" the distance between the lower part of the upper jaw and the upper part of the lower jaw ; this value is much smaller than the true gauge length but it is easier to measure it with accuracy.

The test results are tabulated in table 2 and shown graphically fig. 4.

TABLE 2
TEST RESULTS

Ga uge length mm	10	25	50	100	200	250	300	400
Strands	2560			2570	2520		2450	2490
Kevlar 29 1st batch	2300							1790
Kevlar 29 2nd batch	2410							1920
Kevlar 49	2110	2080	2030			1670		

Test conditions : - non-impregnated rovings and strands
- speed of testing = 10 mm/min

It seems that the roving tensile strength decrease (about 20 %) when the gauge length increase from 10 to 400 mm.

However there is no influence of the gauge length on the strands tensile strength.

- Strands tensile strength distribution

The distribution of tensile strength for Kevlar strands is shown in figure 5. Hundred samples were tested with a 10 mm gauge length and with a 400 mm gauge length. The tensile strength average is 2503 MPa and the standard deviation is 34 MPa for a 400 mm gauge length compared to a 2535 MPa average and a 49 MPa standard deviation for a 10 mm gauge length.

The data distribution for a 10 mm gauge length show a higher stress average but a larger dispersion. However this gauge length influence is small.

In fact, the dispersion is not very important and does not explain the dispersion, usually observed on the cables [3].

3 - RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Ultraviolet stability

Table 3 and figure 6 show the relative (per cent) decreasing properties (flexural strength, flexural modulus, interlaminar shear strength), of Kevlar materials and the tensile strength variation of Kevlar yarn and Kevlar strands (with 10 mm and 400 mm gauge length).

TABLE 3

ULTRAVIOLET STABILITY

Aging time (hours)	KEVLAR 49/EPOXY			KEVLAR 49/PSP				
	Shear loss	Flexural strength loss	Flexural modulus loss	Shear loss	Flexural strength loss	Flexural modulus loss		
24	9	0	0	3	13	14		
100	12	1	9	13	6	0		
200	13	7	9	27	11	5		
400	18	0	0					
500				12	19	11		
	Kevlar 49 4560 den.		Kevlar 49 1420 den.		Kevlar 29 1500 den.		Kevlar 29 8 strands 8x1500 den.	
	10 mm GL	400 mm GL	10 mm GL	400 mm GL	10 mm GL	400 mm GL	10 mm GL	400 mm GL
24	0				13	28	8	
150	12	20	27	49	19	35	19	16
400	23				51	71	43	

Ultraviolet radiations degrade Kevlar fiber but this degradation depends on the gauge length used in tensile test and on the type of Kevlar. Tensile strength of Kevlar roving 4560 deniers decreases of 23 % (after 400 hours) and Kevlar 29 1500 deniers decreases of 51 %, and there is surely denier influence, external fibers protecting internal fiber [6].

In other case, the decrease in strength of Kevlar rovings is more important with 400 mm gauge length.

Kevlar laminates degradation is 20 % maximum after 500 hours, and Kevlar strands degradation is 43 % (after 400 hours).

Kerosene immersion

Loss of mechanical properties after 6 months in kerosene immersion are summarized in table 4.

There is no variation of material properties until 1000 hours. For long time exposure there is a degradation of the materials (30 % for Kevlar 29 and Kevlar 49 fibers, 60 % for strands and from 6 % to 20 % for composites).

But during this test there is a partial Kerosene evaporation after 1000 hours. The liquid concentrate itself in heavy fractionnal parts and tars.

Results of 120°C interlaminar shear strength of Kevlar/epoxy are surprising : results increase after aging and reach the 20° C values.

TABLE 4
KEROSENE EFFECT

Time (hours)	Kevlar/epoxy		Kevlar/PSP ^h		Kevlar 49	Kevlar 29	Kevlar Strands
	Inter. shear loss (per cent)		Inter. shear loss (per cent)		Tensile strength	Tensile strength	Tensile strength
	20° C	120° C	20° C	120° C	20° C	20° C	20° C
24						0	8
100						0	
720 (1 month)	5	- 28	2	2	0		
1000							10
1440 (2 months)	8	- 30	12	7	12		
2500						30	60
4320 (6 months)	8	- 32	6	20	30		

Moisture effect

Experiments of moisture effects of Kevlar 49 strands, Kevlar/epoxy composites and Kevlar/PSP composites were studied. Results are shown in table 5 and in figure 7.

TABLE 5
MOISTURE STABILITY
(all values in MPa)

Test	Kevlar 49		Kevlar/epoxy composite				Kevlar/PSP composite			
	Tension 20° C		Inter. Shear 20° C		Inter. Shear 120° C		Inter. Shear 20° C		Inter. Shear 120° C	
Property	Tensile Strength	Loss %	ISS	Loss %	ISS	Loss %	ISS	Loss %	ISS	Loss %
0	2530		40,7		27,8		20,7		20,2	
1000	2430	4	33,8	17	20,9	25	20,0	3	17,2	15
2000	2440	4	31,7	22	19,7	29				
5000	2440	4	30,5	25	27,5	1	18,0	13	16,6	18

This table show a good stability of Kevlar roving strength. It is known that Kevlar absorbs moisture but this absorption does not affect mechanical properties of the fiber in test conditions. A recent published work does not agree with these results [8].

The stability of Kevlar/PSP composites is better than Kevlar/epoxy composites one. However the decrease of interlaminar shear is always lower than 30 % and the

most part of degradation occurs after 1000 hours aging.

Material properties under high temperatures follow the same evolution as under room temperature.

Salt spray fog effect

Loss of properties of Kevlar/epoxy composites, Kevlar/PSP composites, Kevlar 29 yarn, Kevlar 49 yarn, and Kevlar strands was measured after salt spray aging. Results are shown in table 6

TABLE 6
LOSS PROPERTIES (PER CENT)

Time (hours)	Kevlar/epoxy composite	Kevlar/PSP composite	Kevlar 49 roving	Kevlar 29 roving	Kevlar strands
24				- 4	3
100	10	0	1	- 6	0
1000	4	3	2	1	2
2000	0	19	0		
3000					1
5000	11	5	- 3		

The decrease of Kevlar composites interlaminar shear strength and strands and rovings tensile strength is very small weak (19 % maximum).

The salt spray fog behaviour of Kevlar fiber and Kevlar reinforced materials is very good.

Sea water immersion

After 1000 hours in 4° sea water or in 23° sea water Kevlar 29 and strands tensile strength decreases are less than 10 %.

TABLE 7
SEA WATER AGING

Time (hours)		Kevlar 29 yarn			Strands		
		24	500	1000	24	500	1000
	σ						
Strength loss (per cent)	RT	6	8	9	0	0	1
	4°	1	1	10	5	9	6

These results confirm the good sea water stability announced in the litterature [7]

Immersion in different fluids

Fluids chemical effects on Kevlar 29 rovings and Kevlar strands are shown in table 8.

The properties variations of Kevlar 29 and strands are small, they are lower than 5 % after 1000 hours aging.

TABLE 8
CHEMICAL STABILITY

Fluid	Phari-Nafic Hydraulic fluid			GAI grease			Benzene			ethyl hexyle cebaçate		
	0	24	1000	0	24	1000	0	24	1000	0	24	1000
Kevlar 29 rovings	1920 (150)	1885 (142)	1919 (199)	1920 (150)	1850 (186)	1820 (192)	1920 (150)	1875 (180)	1920 (194)	1920 (150)	1914 (169)	1952 (192)
Kevlar Strands	2423 (124)	2418 (108)	2317 (106)	2496 (64)	2485 (189)	2391 (175)	2522 (74)	2509 (85)	2490 (42)	2423 (124)	2419 (81)	2369 (138)

Tensile strength (standard deviation) in MPa

These results confirm the Kevlar good resistance, as expected in litterature to oils, greases, and solvents [1, 5] .

Thermal cyclic exposure and thermal shock

Results of thermal cyclic exposure are shown in table 9 and in figure 8.

TABLE 9
THERMAL CYCLIC EXPOSURE

Material	Test	Test Temperature	0	200 cycles	500 cycles
Strands	Tension	R ∇	2528 (56)	2093 (105)	2047 (74)
Kevlar 29 rovings	Tension	R ∇	1920 (150)	1809 (128)	1793 (111)
Kevlar 49 rovings	Tension	R ∇	2530 (70)	2349 (140)	2358 (179)
Kevlar/epoxy composite	Inter. shear	R ∇ 120° C	41 (2) 28 (1)	42 (1) 20	41 (1) 20 (3)
Kevlar/PSP composite	Inter. shear	R ∇ 120° C	21 (1) 20 (1)	21 (2) 22 (3)	22 (2) 20 (3)

NB : all values in MPa. Standard deviations in a parentheses.

One can remark the little influence of thermal cyclic on Kevlar composites properties.

A decrease of tensile properties is observed between 0 and 200 cycles but the values are stable after this time.

This decrease is higher for strands (17 % after 500 cycles) than for rovings (7 % after 500 cycles). Kevlar 49 resin impregnated rovings were subjected to - 196° C exposure followed by immediate exposure to + 196° C.

The impregnated roving were tested in tension ; there was no decrease of tensile strength and this is characteristic of undamaged material.

Indeed, we know that a bad impregnation or a short impregnation of the fiber are characteristics of an important decrease of break strength.

Then, this test was made eight times without any deterioration of the impregnated rovings.

CONCLUSIONS

The results of the study show the importance of test conditions for Kevlar yarn, and Kevlar 29 and Kevlar 49 have similar behaviours.

Moisture effect on Kevlar fiber is small and moisture effect on Kevlar composites is depending on the resin but is not large. Ultraviolet radiations affect Kevlar fiber but Kevlar is self protective and therefore its ultraviolet stability is better for larger denier rovings.

Kevlar and Kevlar materials are not damaged in many environments such as : sea water, salt spray fog, benzene, grease, hydraulic fluid and plasticizer. They have moderate stability in Kerosene, particularly after long time aging.

These materials have a good behaviour for thermal shock and a moderate thermal cycle environment resistance.

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FIGURE 1

AGING TESTS

	Composites and Kevlar 49 fibers	Strands and Kevlar 29 fibers
Ultraviolet radiations	×	×
Kerosene immersion	×	×
Moisture	×	
Salt spray (fog)	×	×
Sea water		×
Solvent (benzene)		×
Ethyl hexyl Sebaçate		×
GAI grease		×
Hydraulic fluid		×
Thermal shock	Impregnated Kevlar	
Thermal cyclic exposure	×	×

FIGURE 2

INSTRON PNEUMATIC JAWS

Testing speed influence on the kevlar rovings tensile strength

Gauge length effect on the ultimate stress

FIGURE 4

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FIGURE 5

TENSILE STRENGTH DISTRIBUTIONS ON KEVLAR STRANDS

FIGURE 6

FIGURE 7

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FIGURE 8